

DETERMINATION OF STANDARD ELECTRODE POTENTIAL OF Ag | Ag₂CrO₄, CrO₄²⁻ ELECTRODE

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The standard electrode potential of Ag | Ag₂CrO₄, CrO₄²⁻ electrode has been determined from the studies of the following types of cells :

and the most probable value is found to be -0.4468 at 35°.

The standard electrode potential of Ag | Ag₂CrO₄, CrO₄²⁻ electrode was determined by Cann and Mueller (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*; 1935, 57, 2525) with the help of the cells of the type:

They prepared Ag | AgCl and Ag | Ag₂CrO₄ spiral electrodes electrolytically according to the method of Randell and Young (*ibid.*, 1928, 50, 989). These electrodes did not provide satisfactorily reproducible readings. Their method of calculating the liquid junction potential of the above cells by using the Lewis-Sargent formula does not seem to be sound because this formula is applicable only to a boundary between salts of the same valency type of the same concentration with a common ion. In the present work the following types of the cells have been studied :

EXPERIMENTAL

Stock solutions of potassium chromate (G.R., E. Merck) and potassium sulphate (A.R. B.D.H.) were prepared by weight from their salts. All solutions were prepared by diluting the stock solutions with redistilled water.

Silver chromate was prepared by adding a dilute solution of AgNO₃ (G.R., E. Merck) to a solution of K₂CrO₄ (G.R., E. Merck). The precipitate of Ag₂CrO₄ was washed with K₂CrO₄ solution till free of nitrate, and was kept in a bottle under the same solution.

Pure silver oxalate was prepared by the standard method (*ibid.*, 1948, 70, 3812). The silver oxalate was kept in a bottle under a solution of oxalic acid.

Finely divided silver was deposited on the platinum surface by thermal decomposition of silver oxalate. Silver chromate was washed thoroughly with the solution of K₂CrO₄ to be used in the cell and was kept under the same solution, which was saturated by shaking the flask a number of times. The cell vessel was filled with the suspension of Ag₂CrO₄ and this solution.

The Hg | Hg₂SO₄, K₂SO₄ half elements were prepared as described in "Studies on the Behaviour of uni-bivalent salts in aqueous solution" (unpublished). The methods of checking the half cells and setting up of the cells were as in previous publications from this laboratory (this

Journal, 1951, 28, 683 ; 1954, 31, 480). In every cell combination the molar concentrations of K_2SO_4 and K_2CrO_4 were same. The E.M.F. values of the cells of the type (a) are given in columns 2 (satd. KCl bridge) and 3 (satd. NH_4NO_3 bridge), and the E.M.F. values of the cells of the type (b) are given in column 4, Table I.

E.M.F. readings were taken in duplicate at $35^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ and the duplicates agreed within 0.2 m.v.

TABLE I

Cells of the type used : (a) and (b).

Molar conc. of K_2SO_4/K_2CrO_4 .	Observed E.M.F. (in volt) with			Calc. E.M.F. in volt after correction for l.j.p.	Diff. of cols. (2) & (5).
	Satd. KCl bridge.	Satd. NH_4NO_3 bridge.	No bridge.		
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
0.02	0.1562	0.1565	0.1563	0.1566	0.4 m.v.
0.04	0.1574	0.1578	0.1577	0.1580	0.6
0.05	0.1576	0.1577	0.1578	0.1581	0.5
0.07	0.1582	0.1584	0.1582	0.1585	0.3
0.08	0.1587	0.1589	0.1588	0.1591	0.4
0.10	0.1591	0.1591	0.1592	0.1595	0.4

TABLE II

Molar conc. of K_2SO_4/K_2CrO_4 .	$-E_{SO_4^{2-}}$	Observed E.M.F. with satd. KCl bridge.	$-E_{CrO_4^{2-}}$
	(1)	(2)	(3)
0.02	0.6664 volt	0.1562 volt	0.5102 volt
0.04	0.6616	0.1574	0.5042
0.05	0.6600	0.1576	0.5024
0.07	0.6580	0.1582	0.4998
0.08	0.6565	0.1587	0.4978
0.10	0.6559	0.1591	0.4968

DISCUSSION

Assuming that the liquid junction potential is eliminated by the salt bridges used, the E.M.F. of the cells of the type (a) is represented by

$$E = E_{CrO_4^{2-}} - E_{SO_4^{2-}} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where $E_{CrO_4^{2-}}$ is the E.M.F. of the $Ag | Ag_2CrO_4, K_2CrO_4$ half cell and $E_{SO_4^{2-}}$ is that of the $Hg | Hg_2SO_4, K_2SO_4$ half cell. In cells of the type (b), E.M.F. (E') is represented by

$$E' = E_{CrO_4^{2-}} - E_{SO_4^{2-}} + E_J \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where E_J is the liquid junction potential developed at the boundary of K_2CrO_4 and K_2SO_4 solutions. E.M.F. values measured in the cells of the types (a) and (b) are found nearly same

(differing by not more than 0.3 m.v.). Henderson's equation for the potential difference between solutions used reduces itself to

$$E_J = \frac{RT}{2F} \log_e \frac{UK^+ + V\frac{1}{2}SO_4^{2-}}{UK^+ + V\frac{1}{2}CrO_4^{2-}} \quad \dots (3)$$

In the above expression U and V denote the ionic conductances of the ions indicated. The calculated value of E_J is found to be -0.3 m.v. which agrees well with the observed values (Table I).

With the help of $E_{SO_4^{2-}}$ obtained (under publication) the value of $E_{CrO_4^{2-}}$ (given in col. 4, Table II) for each concentration of K_2CrO_4 is calculated from equation (1) using E.M.F. values of cell 'a' with saturated KCl.

By applying the Debye-Hückel limiting equation, $E^\circ_{CrO_4^{2-}}$ is calculated from the relation,

$$E_{CrO_4^{2-}} - \frac{RT}{2F} \log_e C_{CrO_4^{2-}} + \frac{RT}{2F} \times 4A\sqrt{\mu} = E^\circ_{CrO_4^{2-}} + \frac{RT}{2F} \times B\mu \quad \dots (4)$$

by plotting the left hand side against μ , and it is found to be -0.4464.

Saturated KCl may not be able to eliminate completely the liquid junction potential. On comparison of the E.M.F. values given in column 2 (using saturated KCl bridge), column 3 (using saturated NH_4NO_3 bridge), and column 5 (obtained by subtracting the calculated value of E_J from E') in Table I, it is found that NH_4NO_3 bridge is better in this case. Using E.M.F. values in column 5, the value of $E^\circ_{CrO_4^{2-}}$ comes to be -0.4468. So, the most probable value of $E^\circ_{CrO_4^{2-}}$ will be -0.4468 volt. The various errors in the work of Cann and Mueller (*loc. cit.*) seem to have cancelled one another to a large extent (their value being -0.4463 volt).

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